

The Critical-Philology-Paradigm
and
Our Ādhyātmika Tradition

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The Critical-Philology-Paradigm and Our *ādhyātmika* Tradition

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ABSTRACT

During recent decades a lot of writings, diametrically opposed to our traditional view, have come from the West declaring Sanskrit writings devoid of any spirituality, full of internal contradictions, divisive, and above all created for power-culture manipulations, and hence oppressive, immoral and socially toxic. Our Tradition's viewpoint, however, has always been the "bliss", *ānanda*; *viñānam anandaṁ brahma*; SB.14.6.9.34; BṛhU.3.9.34), of the "Cosmic Whole" through *puruṣārtha*, that is why it invokes, *sarvé bhavantu sukhinaḥ* , *sarvé santu nirāmayāḥ* | *sarvé bhadrāṇi pashyantu* , *mā kashchid_duḥkha-bhāg-bhavét* ||. If one finds an "exploitative-power-culture-manipulation" in such a viewpoint, which assimilates *sarvé*, i.e., "all", into its bliss invocation, there must be something wrong in one's reasoning. Many of the mistakes are committed when we continue using mindlessly some Paradigm or methodology without really knowing if it is applicable to the subject under consideration. Every method depends on certain assumptions and success or failure of the method depends on whether foundational assumptions are satisfied or not. In this paper, we explore the foundations of the Western literary analytics, the "Critical Theory - Philology Project - Paradigm", applied by Western practitioners to our Sanskrit Knowledge System and Scriptures, and examine their applicability to our Sanskrit Knowledge System, especially that part dealing with the *ādhyātmika* dimension. Causes limiting the Paradigm responsible for previously mentioned insinuating interpretations have been found and modifications are proposed to widen and generalize the foundational assumptions to enhance the applicability of the Paradigm, and so to assimilate the part, which has been assumed away so far. This dismissal of a vital aspect of our traditional paradigm may be due to conceptual handicap, technical limitation or lack of tractability or to dominance of the leftist ideology or a combination of all these. Examination of these may be undertaken, as challenging research projects, both, by Indian and/or the Western scholars since what is proposed here would lead to methodological innovation.

Keywords: Critical Theory, Marx, dialectical, materialistic, Philology, Vico, Spinoza, Hegel, Hume, Coomaraswamy, gesture, mirror, imagination, emancipation, contradictions, poststructuralism, Derrida, deconstruction, Mahabharata, hierarchization, aestheticization, Sheldon Pollock, Jan Gonda, rationality, idealism, Theory, practice, criticism, literary, transcendental, Sanskrit, *pāramārthika* , *kāma* ,*puruṣārtha*, *mokṣa*, *vyāvahārika*, *ākālīka*, *alārīkāra*, *mīmāṃsā*, *Vedānta*, *pramāṇa*, *ādhyātmika*, *aitihāsika*, *anādi*

1.0.0 Introduction

Philosophy in India", (which its Sanskrit Knowledge System principally carries) is essentially spiritual." wrote Dr. Radhakrishnan (1993, 24-25), "It is the intense spirituality of India, and not any great political structure or social organization that it has developed, that has enabled it to resist the ravages of time and the accidents of history. External invasions and internal dissensions came very near crushing its civilization many times in its history. The Greek and the Scythian, the Persian and the Mogul, the French and the English have by turn attempted to suppress it, and it has its head held high. India has not been finally subdued, and its old flame of spirit is still burning. Throughout its life, it has been living with one purpose. It has fought for truth and against error ... The history of Indian thought illustrates the endless quest of the mind, ever old, ever new". Our

Tradition's viewpoint has always been, the *ānanda*; (*viñānam anandaṁ brahma*, SB.14.6.9.34; BṛhU.3.9.34), of the "Cosmic Whole" through *puruṣārtha*, that is why invocation:

sarvé bhavantu sukhinaḥ ,
sarvé santu nirāmayāḥ |
sarvé bhadrāṇi pashyantu ,
mā kashchid_duḥkha-bhāg-bhavét ||,

Practitioners of the "Critical Theory-Philology Project-Paradigm", (hereafter, CPP), Western and Indians trained in it, alike, during the last few decades, have been giving a diametrically opposite view, where our Sanskrit Knowledge System, has been declared to be devoid of any spirituality, full of internal contradictions, divisive, artificially created for power-culture manipulations, and

hence oppressive, immoral and socially toxic. If one finds an exploitative "power-culture manipulation", (Pollock, 2006), in such a viewpoint which assimilates *sarvé*, i.e., "all", into its bliss invocation, there must be something wrong in one's reasoning. Many serious concerns due to such interpretations have been raised from time to time, including Mr. Rajiv Malhotra's, 'The Battle for Sanskrit', (Malhotra. 2016). Many of the mistakes are committed when we persist in using mindlessly some Paradigm or methodology without really knowing if it is applicable to the subject under consideration. This makes it necessary to make a careful and Critical scrutiny of the ideological foundations and Paradigm underlying the Western Critical-Philology and the writings under this Paradigm.

In the post-structuralist phase of the Critical Theory, Michel Foucault (Foucault,1979),made the observation that in the Western societies, the social power may get mediated through philosophy and described the way in which, the latent struggle between the social authority and individual reason can turn the reason into a battle ground. Sheldon Pollock, known to be the leader of such Philological exercises, applied the same to the Indian tradition, assuming that the same Foucauldian process might have taken place in the Indian intellectual tradition, in the field of ideas. He considered Sanskrit texts as a mediator to the authority, who prescribed action and thereby acting as a career of prescriptions into the lives, and onto the bodies, of those who enacted the Indian philosophies of law, *Nāṭya*, dance etc. Based on that Sheldon Pollock writes, "Voluntaristic vernacularism' and 'non-coercive cosmopolitanism', along with 'transcendental Paradigmatism' and 'argumentative pluralism', will convince some that Macaulay was right when he declared India to be the 'strangest of all possible anomalies.'" (Pollock, 2015, d). The 'true intent' behind such studies and statements, however, lies somewhere else as Grünendahl, (2010) points while thinking on possible corrections "... it would be futile to exhaust oneself in the tedious correction of factual errors and distortions, because the postcolonial charge gathers its momentum outside the sphere of prosaic factuality, preferably by means of subtle insinuation." See section 4.0.0., below for further details. Every civilization has developed ways of interpreting the texts that it produces. We know that our own tradition has welcomed various interpretations proposed from time to time throughout its intellectual history, but never

accepted any unless it was passed through rigorous tests, through logic, arguments and 'inner' experience¹, (Gopal,1983). Our tradition's viewpoint has always been that of the "Cosmic whole". Everyone has by certain presuppositions, knowingly or unknowingly, determined by his or her own socio-cultural background and the tradition he or she belongs to, which may lead to a specific interpretation based on that, unless his tradition itself warns him to liberate himself from such strings. Fortunately, our Indian tradition knew it quite well and to eliminate any possible misinterpretation, directs to one to lift oneself to a state of absolute indifference, (Sati Shankar, 2015).

In his "Towards a Political Philology, Sheldon Pollock, writes, "... it may not always be possible to draw a perfectly straight line between a Philological method and a 'Critical Theory' of culture and power...", (Pollock,2008,52). Philology and Critical Theory combine, or better call it the Critical Philology Paradigm, as applied and practiced by the previously mentioned practitioners, is based on "Vico-Spinoza-Marx-Critical Theoretic-Philological Project-Paradigm", (Sati Shankar, 2016). Careful scrutiny of this Paradigm and the underlying assumptions in its foundations makes its inherent limitations explicit. Once we know that, we will come to realize how and why the practitioners of the said Paradigm, even if they follow their methodology ethically and professionally, are intellectually imprisoned and misleading interpretations of our holistic tradition becomes inevitable. Prof. Pollock, while repeatedly referring to Philology as his "the methodology", carefully keeps the "Critical Theory", in the

¹ While talking of *S'aastras* and their association with *ādhyātṃika*, it is interesting to note that *VyaakaraNa* in the Paniniyan tradition, Linguistics /Grammar too, is shown to be a means of spiritual practice.

आसन्नं ब्रह्मणस् तस्य तपसाम् उत्तमं तपः /प्रथमं छन्दसाम् अङ्गम् आहुर
व्याकरणं बुधाः // वाक्य_१।११ //

Since speech is such a focus of study (along side mind/psyche, the subject matter of psychology and the like) that an individual is compelled to self-reflect to get a grasp of it. Such a self-reflection , introspection, *antarmukhataa*, as a means of spiritual saadhanaa is well established. In the same book *Vaakyapadeeyam*, *Yoga* is called *Aadhyaatma S'aastra*.

कायवाग्बुद्धिविषया ये मलाः समवस्थिताः / चिकित्सालक्षणाध्यात्म-
शास्त्रैस् तेषां विशुद्धयः // वाक्य_१।१७४ . (BVP, 2016).

background. Moreover, in his writings, he rarely gives direct references or keywords relating to the Critical Theory'. Section 2.0.0., below, introduces some salient features and concepts from Marxism, a prerequisite for the Critical Theory and Philology without which it is difficult, if not impossible, to understand the foundations of these disciplines and also some of the practitioner's malpractices. Similarly, Section 3.0 introduces essential concepts from the Critical Theory and section 4.0 from Philology. In section 5.0.0., we examine the appropriateness of the Critical-Philology Paradigm as applied by its practitioners to the Sanskrit Knowledge System. We find that the "Vico-Spinoza - Marx - Critical - theoretic - Philological project-Paradigm", (Sati Shankar, 2016), which, Pollock has been applying to the SKS, is inappropriate to deal with it because of its dialectical - historical - materialist - assumptions, which assume away the ideological /transcendental/ metaphysical part at the very initial stage. Attempts made to assimilate the transcendental/metaphysical elements at the later stage, but only by reducing them to the psychobiological phenomena in nature. Such an approach still fails to represent the "Cosmic Whole" Paradigm integral to most Indian soteriological systems. Section 6.0 is devoted to concluding remarks and a few proposals followed by references.

2.0.0. The Critical Theory-Philology Project-Paradigm

"If one wants to conduct a Critical analysis," writes Fuchs, "..., one requires a Critical philosophy as a foundation. The most important Critical philosophy tradition is the one that goes back to Hegel and Marx." (Fuchs, 2015, 12). However, before that, we need to be familiar with Giambattista Vico, "the first Marxist before Marx" whose Theory lies at the heart of the Marxism and the Critical Theory and Philology. 'It is said that Giambattista Vico, and not Spinoza, is the first Marxist before Marx. He anticipated anticolonial liberation Theory, and he spoke directly to while giving us weapons against, the post-humanism of internet culture.' (Brennan, 2013). Vico inspired Marx, besides many others with his three stage in humanity, 'divine-heroic-human', as envisaged by the poets, whom he considered to be the "creators"; this is not unlike the role of *kavis*, in our own tradition, (Coomaraswamy, 1994, 98, fn. 97).

2.1.0. To see the first steps in Vico's writings, it is necessary to consider four basic rules concerning knowledge acceptability of René Descartes. The rules were: (1). 'never to accept anything for true not clearly known to be such; (2) 'to divide difficulties examined into as many parts as possible;'(3).' start with the simplest and easiest, ascend to the more complex, pay attention to the asymmetric relation of antecedence and sequence and (4)'make enumerations and reviews to assure that nothing was omitted,'(Descartes, 1637). Vico criticized Descartes for reflecting only on nature's empirical reality and not on human ability to 'create' new realities.' Vico gave the verum-factum principle and the ideal eternal history, which became his two most famous ideas. According to the verum-factum principle, one can know the truth in what one makes. According to Vico, 'because God made the natural world, only God can know it. Humans can understand the human world because humans made it. This became the foundation for a 'New Science', (Vico, 1948/1744). Vico gave another justification against Descartes' famous "I think, therefore I am". According to Vico, this statement was to provide a "first principle" that refutes skepticism, but it did not address entirely the challenge of the skeptics. A skeptic knows that he or she exists. However, he or she 'does not know anything significant about his existence, because the 'cause of his or her ideas' remains unknown. This presented a serious challenge to Cartesianism. 'The *verum-factum* principle claimed to solve the skeptic's problem by explaining that since "we are the cause of what we make, we can know what was made". Thus, the skeptic, who claims, "knowledge is impossible", is incorrect. For Vico, making something becomes the criteria for knowing the truth about it.' In his later writings, however, Vico holds that 'through the world, humans make (and so they know it), humans can also witness "eternal truth" such as the "ideal eternal history" and the *verum-factum* principle itself.' Vico suggested that the *verum-factum* principle ought to be read in conjunction with the *verum-certum* principle outlined in the 'Universal Law'. According to Vico, 'we begin with certum, acquaintance with and beliefs about particular matters of fact, which is a precondition of all thoughts and actions and is capable of attaining *verum*, knowledge of 'universal truths.' Its conceptual implications become clear with the development of the dialectical historical materialism in Marxism over which we will have a look below. What follows is based on the "Dialectical and Historical Materialism", an article

by J.V. Stalin, (Stalin. 1938). All quotes are from the same source unless stated otherwise, and paper may be referred to for further details.

2.2.0. Dialectical-Historical Materialism

2.2.1. To establish the 'dialectical method, Marx adopted Hegel's philosophy of which the main feature has been dialectical, took its "rational kernel" and left the "idealistic" part, and with that developed a dialectics with the rational kernel further so as to lend it a modern scientific form.

2.2.2. 'To describe materialism, Marx usually refers to Feuerbach as the philosopher who restored materialism, but took the "inner kernel", the materialistic part, from Feuerbach's philosophy, leaving "its idealistic and religious-ethical encumbrances", and developed it into a scientific-philosophical Theory of materialism.

2.2.3. 'Dialectical materialism is an approach which presupposes that the method of studying and apprehending the phenomena of nature is "dialectical" while its interpretation of the phenomena of nature, its conception, its Theory, are necessarily materialistic.'

2.3.0. Marx developed his Dialectical Method with the following features:

'The dialectical method of thought was later extended to the phenomena of nature, presupposed to be in constant movement and undergoing constant change, and that it develops because of 'inherent contradictions' in nature, as the result of the interaction of opposed forces in nature.'

2.3.1. *Contrary to Metaphysics*, 'Nature is Connected and Deterministic: All phenomena are 'inseparably connected with, and conditioned by the surrounding phenomena.'

2.3.2. *Contrary to Metaphysics*, 'Nature is in a State of Continuous Motion and Change, i.e., dynamic: "Phenomena are not only interconnected and interdependent in nature but also they change continuously so are their development, their coming into being and going out of being." (Inherent change)

2.3.3. *Contrary to Metaphysics*, 'Natural Quantitative Change Leads to Qualitative Change: Dialectics " holds that the process of development as defined above are not mere cyclical repetitions

of events "but as an onward and upward movement, as a transition from an old qualitative state to a new qualitative state, as a development from the simple to the complex, from the lower to the higher." This makes historicity an indispensable in not only the Marxism but also its allied developments, the Critical Theory.

Another important characteristic in Marxism is Contradiction in Phenomena. The role of contradictions in Marxist process was put on a pedestal by Mao Zedong (also pronounced as Mao Tse Tung) in his article "On Contradictions", (Zedong.1937, 1937, b). 'Contradictions' as states of affair lie at the heart of the whole Marxism and its subsequent developments and have significant applications to Critical theories, to be seen in the next section.

2.3.4. *Contrary to Metaphysics*, Contradictions are inherent in Nature: "Dialectics holds that internal contradictions are inherent in all things and phenomena of nature, for they all have their negative and positive sides, the past and a future, something dying away and something developing; and that the struggle between these opposites, the struggle between the old and the new, between that which is dying away and that which is being born, between that which is disappearing and that which is developing, constitutes the internal content of the process of development, the internal content of the transformation of quantitative changes into qualitative changes." Along with the historicity, contradictions let to such conceptualizations in phenomena as 'binary structures', in Levi Strauss's structuralism, hierarchism, and later works of Derrida, Foucault, and Rorty etc. in the post-structuralist Critical Theory.

2.3.5. One interesting fact with the analytics of 'contradictions' is that Marxism does not attempt to eliminate these contradictions but leaves them to fight and let some result come up by itself. Interestingly, the Theory of contradiction remains in action to analyze and find out further hidden contradictions and again to leave them to decide by themselves and the process continues, hence there is a continuous tussle in the society, which to Marxism is the cause of progress, for details (Habib, 2010). Its direct effect can be found in writings under Marxist and Critical Theory Paradigms, as introduced in the next section.

2.4.0. Marx gave his Philosophical Materialism with the following features

2.4.1. *Contrary to idealism, Materialist:* "Marx's philosophical materialism holds that the world is by its very nature material, and there is no need of a "universal spirit".

2.4.2. *Contrary to idealism, Reality:* Idealism asserts that 'only our consciousness really exists, and that the material world, being, nature, exists only in our consciousness' in our sensations, ideas, and perceptions. The Marxist philosophical materialism holds "that matter, nature, being, is an "objective reality" existing outside and independent of our consciousness; that matter is primary, since it is the source of sensations, ideas, consciousness, and that consciousness is secondary, derivative, since it is a reflection of matter, a reflection of being; that thought is a product of matter which in its development has reached a high degree of perfection, namely, of the brain, and the brain is the organ of thought; and that, therefore, one cannot separate thought from matter without committing a grave error."

2.4.3. *Contrary to idealism,* "The question of the relation of thinking to being, the relation of spirit to nature is the paramount question of the whole of philosophy... The answers, which the philosophers gave to this question, split them into two great camps. Those who asserted the primacy of spirit to nature ... comprised the camp of idealism. The others, who regarded nature as primary, belong to the various schools of materialism." (Marx, Selected Works, Vol. I, p. 329.) Quoted in (Stalin. 1938).

2.4.4. Marx says, "The material, sensuously perceptible world to which we ourselves belong is the only reality... Our consciousness and thinking, however, supra-sensuous they may seem, are the product of a material, bodily organ, the brain. The matter is not a product of the mind, but the mind itself is merely the highest product of matter." quoted in (Stalin. 1938).

2.4.5. "The world picture is a picture of how matter moves and of how 'matter thinks ... The brain is the organ of thought."

2.5.0. *Contrary to idealism, The World and Its Laws Are Knowable,*

Idealism, which denies the possibility of knowing the world and its laws, which does not believe in the authenticity of our knowledge, does not

recognize objective truth, and holds that the world is full of "things-in-themselves" that can never be known to science, Marxist philosophical materialism holds that the world and its laws are fully knowable, that our knowledge of the laws of nature, tested by experiment and practice, is authentic knowledge having the validity of objective truth, and that there are no things in the world which are unknowable, but only things which are as yet not known, but which will be disclosed and made known by the efforts of science and practice." Here we can be compared Vico with it.

2.6.0. Study of the history of society becomes a science.

2.6.1. "If the connection between the phenomena of nature and their interdependence are laws of the development of nature, it follows, too, that the connection and interdependence of the phenomena of social life are laws of the development of society, and not something accidental."

2.6.2. "Hence, social life, the history of society, ceases to be an agglomeration of "accidents", for, the history of society becomes a development of society according to regular laws, and the study of the history of society becomes a science."

2.6.3. "Hence, the science of the history of society, despite all the complexity of the phenomena of social life, can become as precise a science as, let us say, biology, and capable of making use of the laws of development of society for practical purposes."

2.7.0. Material world is primary, and consciousness, thought, is secondary

2.7.1. "If nature, being, the material world, is primary, and consciousness, thought, is secondary, derivative; if the material world represents objective reality existing independently of the consciousness of men, while consciousness is a reflection of this objective reality, it follows that the material life of society, its being, is also primary, and its spiritual life secondary, derivative, and that the material life of society is an objective reality existing independently of the will of men, while the spiritual life of society is a reflection of this objective reality, a reflection of being."

2.7.2. "Hence, the source of formation of the spiritual life of society, the origin of social ideas,

social theories, political views and political institutions, should not be sought for in the ideas, theories, views and political institutions themselves, but in the conditions of the material life of society, in social being, of which these ideas, theories, views, etc., are the reflection."

2.7.3. "Hence, if in different periods of the history of society different social ideas, theories, views and political institutions are to be observed; if under the slave system we encounter certain social ideas, theories, views and political institutions, under feudalism others, and under capitalism others still, this is not to be explained by the "nature", the "properties" of the ideas, theories, views and political institutions themselves but by the different conditions of the material life of society at different periods of social development."

2.7.4. "Whatever is the being of a society, whatever are the conditions of material life of a society, and such are the ideas, theories political views and political institutions of that society."

2.7.5. "Theory becomes a material force as soon as it has gripped the masses." (Marx and Engels, Vol. I, p. 406.) Quoted in (Stalin. 1938).

2.8.0. Historical Materialism

'Historical materialism is an application of the principles of dialectical materialism to the phenomena of the life of society, to the study of society and of its history, in its broadest sense. In its essence, dialectics is the direct opposite of metaphysics and explores dynamic changes, i.e., changes through time and contradictions.' "In production," Marx says", men not only act on nature but also on one another. They produce only by co-operating in a certain way and mutually exchanging their activities. In order to produce, they enter into definite connections and relations with one another and only within these social connections and relations does their action on nature, does production, take place." (Marx and Engels, Vol. V, p. 429.)" Quoted in (Stalin. 1938).

2.9.0. How Marxists view Literature

Let us begin our inquiry with a question, 'how, after all, is the art and literature viewed in Marxism?'

2.9.1. For, the Marxists follow Engels' lead as he said on Goethe, "We criticize him not from a moral or from a Party point of view, but at the very most from the aesthetic and historical point of view; we measure Goethe neither by moral nor by political,

nor by 'human' standards" (Marx & Engels 1976, 356),

2.9.2. What he wrote to Ferdinand Lassalle for play, Franz von Sickingen:

"You see that I make very high, that is to say, the very highest demands on your work both from the aesthetic and historical points of view ..." (Marx & Engels 1976, 107).

2.10.0. Thus, we see that the dual yardsticks are:

- (i) Aesthetics and Form and
- (ii) Historicity.

We can see the influence of these developments on later developments of Critical theories and Philology. We end this summary here with essentials of Marxism needed initially for the conceptual understanding of The Critical Theory and beyond, in the next section.

3.0.0. Critical Theory

The term "Critical Theory, was in fact, used as a camouflage by the Marxist theorists of famous Frankfurt Institute of Germany, who ran away after the Nazi's intervention to take exile in Columbia University, New York, the United States, which is by chance, the base of Pollock also. Critical Theory is an approach that studies society under Marxist-dialectical-historical-materialism, by analyzing the political economy, domination, contradiction, exploitation, and ideologies. It is a "normative approach" which considers "domination, or "hierarchization", as a problem", which provided ground for the "binary" principle in the structuralism of Lavi Strauss and at the poststructuralist stage, to the deconstruction of Derrida, Foucauldian, and Rorty, to name a prominent few and aims at a domination-free society through the political struggles with leftist ideology.

'If one wants to conduct a Critical analysis of ..., one requires a Critical philosophy as a foundation. The most important Critical philosophy tradition is the one that goes back to Hegel and Marx.' (Fuchs, 2015, 12). The summary below is based on (Corradetti, 2016). All quotes, direct or indirect, are from the same source unless stated otherwise, refer the main source for further details.

3.1.0 There are two primary tasks of the Critical Social Theory:

- (i) Analysis of 'Theory and practice' relation and
- (ii) The criticism of 'ideologies' with respect to their emergence, social evolution, power-culture, and historicity.

While applying to Textual analysis, the primary tasks mentioned in (3.1.0.) above with (2.9.0), are combined together for the analysis with respect to their textual forms, genres, textual readings , aesthetics and historicity, and to derive certain "sense" in accordance with the objects of the "Philology project". This has been clarified in (4.1.0.). It is this activity, which leads to, what is known as Philology. All of these activities can be observed at once in (Pollock, 2006, 1985), for example.

3.2.0. Traditionally, there have been two approaches to the analysis of the Theory and Practice:

- (i) A cognitive approach to validation of a moral statement,
- (ii) A non-cognitive approach where no truth validity is defended,

Critical Theory added two more grounds to it:

- (i) '*anthropological*', where the transcendental argument is combined with it with the argument that 'humans have 'interest', in knowledge so long as it is meant for preservation of 'Self-Identity and then, to preserve one's self-identity, humans go beyond, 'mere compliance with 'biological survival', (Habermas, 1968) (in Ingram and Simon Ingram, 1992, 263) and
- (ii) '*psychological*'. The 'psychological' aspect of the Theory and practice makes use of Freud's 'psychoanalysis', David Hume's "where 'is' and 'ought' are strictly separated and an attempt is made to 'unmask false 'ought' by psychoanalysis to clarify the mechanism of constructing 'desires'. The greatest philosophical role of psychoanalysis in the Frankfurt School led to the interpretation of 'interest genealogy'. In our context, these are the techniques used to justify the exclusion of the transcendence from the Critical Theory and CPP.

3.3.0. Rejection of Non-Cognitive Approach

'Critical Theory rejects, the non-cognitive approach based on (3.2.0.), "as it cannot provide justifications for the difference between the norm-guided ' behavioral convergence' and the "reason" or justification behind 'following a valid rule or norm' where validity may require an extra layer of justification of the norm being followed. Pollock's

critique of Indian intellectual tradition, (Pollock, 1985) and *mīmāṃsā* (Pollock, 1989) are the case in point. To establish his arguments, against the non-cognitive approach, Habermas uses the device of the 'counter-factual.' His arguments strengthen criticism of 'positivism and of the 'epistemic status of knowledge."

Following Marx, see (2.4.2.) above, there can be no 'objective knowledge' in the Critical Theory as defined by positivists, independent of the 'inter-subjective forms of understanding'. One of the weakest points in the Critical Theory is the fact that "knowledge is strictly embedded in serving human interests", therefore, it cannot be considered as 'value-neutral' and 'objectively independent'. This represents as one of the most dangerous implications of the Critical Theory, one that culminated in a deconstructive Philology leading to a stage where, "... knowledge is simultaneously reduced to mere interpretation, and, according to the deconstructionist axiom, all interpretation is a misinterpretation. Thus, all knowledge is provisional or hypothetical, with the obvious exception of the deconstructionist's knowledge of this being so; all readings are misreadings since no reading can escape correction and consequently, all texts are subject to deconstruction, Critical editions being just one subset." (Grünendahl, 2010).

The 'psychological' aspect of the Theory and practice makes use of 'psychoanalysis' "where is and ought are strictly separated and an attempt is made to 'unmask false 'ought' by psychoanalysis to clarify the mechanism of constructing 'desires'. The greatest philosophical role of psychoanalysis in the Frankfurt School led to the interpretation of 'interest genealogy' which says, further, "To hide their unresolved 'tensions' Individuals use 'Imagination', to reconcile with social realities, through 'aestheticization' of basic instincts liberated through imagination. 'Based on his criticism of non-cognitive arguments, Habermas states, "knowledge is thus grounded into the practical domain, 'interest' and is reflected into self-reflection, i.e., 'knowledge for the sake of knowledge'", (Habermas, 1968) in (in Ingram and Simon Ingram, 1992. 263).

3.4.0. The Mirror of Reality: Ideology and Critique

With the 'Theory' or "ought", the traditional theory explains facts through presumed universal laws, which are verifiable, and must be verified empirically, as we do in scientific investigations.

Knowledge of phenomena is considered a "mirror of reality". It implies that the condition of truth and falsehood presupposes an 'ideal' objective structure of the world. This is firmly rejected by Critical Theory. Horkheimer, the founder of the Critical Theory, and his followers, following Marx, see (2.5.0.), rejected such objectivity with the plea that object of knowledge itself is 'embedded in a historical and social process'. To him, 'objectivity was a myth,' because it depends on 'technological conditions', which in turn, is sensitive to the material condition of production, i.e., stages of socio-economic development in the society.

As we have seen above, the Critical Theory finds "knowledge as "mirror of reality", nothing more than mere a theoretical proposition thereby making knowledge independent of social affairs. This is another reason behind the failure of Critical Theory, initial or developed, to cope partially with our Sanskrit Knowledge System. In addition, it gives us the first indication of what methodological modification we may need to deal with both, the Indian knowledge system and the Critical reasoning Paradigm of the West.

To Critical Theory, following Marx, knowledge is social criticism, which in turn, transforms itself into social action and ultimately into reality, sees (2.6.0. and 2.7.0.) This is what we find in the Critical Theory, Karl Marx's dialectical materialism, which he developed, based on Hegel, where he aimed to reconcile socio-historical contradictions, Marx's Theory of economy and society, and Hegel's bourgeois philosophy. Also like Marx, "Critical Theory rejects Hegel's metaphysical apparatus and also the 'eschatological' aspect of Marx's Theory and analyses and aims for the open system of analysis based on the "immanent form of social criticism". Critical Theory expanded Marx's ideas to formulate 'social emancipatory strategies'. Contrary to 'the methods of objectified knowledge', the Critical Theory 'serves the purpose of "human emancipation" through self-reflection and consciousness'.

We know that the primary tasks of the Critical Social Theory have been, (i) Exploration of relation between the Theory and practice, i.e., what ought to be and what is, to use David Hume's terms and (ii) criticism of ideologies The ideology in the Critical Theory, is considered to be a set of belief denoting some worldview, or some Paradigm' based on the 'biological and quasi-biological properties' or, the 'cultural or socio-cultural

features' of the group, and alternate ways of social bonds and causalities in the society are decided through this. 'In addition to propositional contents or performatives, it includes 'gesture', ceremonies' etc, (Gauss, 1981, 6-8). Hence, the 'Critical Theory abandons the 'idealistic' naive conception of knowledge.' on the grounds that 'the intellectuals are part of this world and are not external observers, the knowledge they obtain is from the social system itself due to interdependence as founded in Marxism we have seen above.'

3.4.0. Historicity

The historicity of dialectical materialism in Marxism comes as one of the foundation stones in Critical Theory, which through ideological criticism discovers the "wrong rationalizations of present and past injustices'. Since this activity forms a significant part of the basic task of Critical Theory, it makes the assumption of historicity unavoidable in the Critical analysis. Once again we encounter a significant point where Marxian linear historicity inherent in the Critical Theory makes this Paradigm inapplicable to the Cyclical time Paradigm of the Indian knowledge Tradition.

3.5.0. Imagination

The Critical Theory works between the two ends, the Theory, which may be treated as equivalent to David Hume's "what ought to be", on one hand, and the practice, again in Hume's terms, "what is" on the other. 'It is. Therefore, neither a pure science in the sense of Marx nor a philosophy' but, in fact, an analytical method used to 'clarify socio-political determinants of certain philosophical views', and of transcending the use of 'imagination'.

3.6.0. Rationality

Rationality lies at the heart of scientific methods, be it the methods in social sciences, or theoretical or mathematical sciences or natural sciences. In the Critical Theory of the 'Frankfurt School, rationality was considered to be a 'historical' process and 'the unity of rationality and the historical process' was taken as a "precondition for social criticism", but later on, under the influence of post-modernity, this unity got broken. '(Coradetti, 2016).

Critical Theory takes rationality in two ways:

- (i) " as a 'dominant form of power deprived of any normative force' and
- (ii) As a 'liberating force based on yet to come scenario."

'Critical Theory gives rise to a form of knowledge after analysis and criticism of what it calls the "falsity of conscience". (Geuss 1981, 26). It forms a ground for Critical theorists and philologists while dealing with *pāramārthika*. Such an analysis of "falsity of conscience" leads to two notions, "true and false interests", which can be separated by two approaches, one, 'perfect knowledge approach' and second, 'optimal condition approach' (Geuss, 1981, 48). "Based on his criticism of non-cognitive arguments, Habermas states, "knowledge is thus grounded into the practical domain, 'interest' and is reflected into self-reflection, i.e., 'knowledge for the sake of knowledge'", (Habermas, 1968) in (in Ingram and Simon Ingram, 1992.263).

3.7.0. Critical Theory: Post-Structuralism and beyond

Poststructuralism brought many changes to Critical Theory, as far as analytics is concerned. 'Conflicting models of the Critical Theory are being utilized by different individuals and groups in various fields of inquiry in different parts of the world. There is also a tendency to combine Critical theories in one's work, following Foucault', (Foucault, 1979). Under the influence of the Structuralism, due to Levi-Straus and post-structuralism in France, Critical Theory has developed into a truly interdisciplinary methodology with which culminated into "The Critical Theory". Interventions by Derrida, (Derrida,1977), and his "Deconstruction", as well as other post-structural theories, declines the structuralist assumption that structural principles are essences, that there are universal structural principles of language which exist 'before' the incidence of language.

"All 'principles' of existence (i.e., of experience) are historically situated and are structured by the interplay of individual experience and institutional force, through the language, symbols, environment, exclusions and oppositions of the moment (and of the previous moments through which this one is constructed). Structures are historical, temporary, contingent, operating through differentiation and displacement."

3.7.1. One point, important for our purpose is the fact that unlike the Critical Theory, "Deconstruction does not deny the existence of an independent, physical world."

However, it is pointed out that, "if deconstruction seems to oppose Humanism, it is because Humanism operates by substituting the concept 'man' for the concept 'God'(or 'order', 'nature', 'Truth', 'logos', etc.) and so placing 'man' as the unproblematic ground of meaningfulness for human life. It should be clear; however, that 'man' is then a hypothesized center, substituting for another hypothesized center, in the history of metaphysics. Deconstruction wants to clarify the instability upon which such a concept is grounded." Further, "deconstructive reading can be applied to any text. It is a Theory of reading, not a Theory of literature. Derrida generally deconstructs philosophical writing, showing the metaphysical contradictions and the historicity of writing which lay claim to the absolute. ". The more 'metaphysical' or universal and 'meaningful' a text the more powerfully it can provoke deconstructive reading; similarly as 'reading as literature' implies a raising of meaning to the highest level of universality, 'reading as literature' also calls forth the potential for a strong counter-reading. As Derrida says, "the more it is written, the more it shakes up its own limits or lets them be thought". (Lye, 1996)

'The Critical Theory now is a multidisciplinary, multidimensional term that continues to take on differing connotations and uses, applied to many different disciplines and debates in the contemporary moment. The most important fact is that "there is no single Critical Theory that can deal with multiple trajectories and dimensions." It now combines social Theory, cultural and political commentary, philosophy, literary stylistics, and many social and human sciences in their work, crossing boundaries between academic disciplines and fields.'

4.0.0. Philology

It is interesting, to begin with, what Brennan says. He writes, "Even in an era of the false populism of youth techno-cultures where intellectual dialogue seems dead on arrival, a political riposte of sorts is possible. It will find its resources in the apparently belated idea of "Philology" – not understood as the old hoary science of the 19th-century paleographic text, but a generalist, sociological quest for meanings as intentions. And in fact, Philology has found a new popularity recently for just that reason." (Brennan, 2013).

We have seen above that the primary tasks of the Critical Theory, when applied to Textual analysis, has been to perform (i) Analysis of relation between the 'Theory and practice' and (ii) the criticism of 'ideologies' with respect to their textual forms, textual readings, aesthetics, and historicity, and it is this activity which led to what is known as Philology. The grounds for textual analysis and 'intents' behind taking directions to 'make sense' out of that, may come from sources other than the Critical Theory as well. It is an analytical method involving deconstruction used to 'clarify socio-political determinants of certain views', and of 'transcending the use of 'imagination' and hence "making some sense" out of the texts. Further, below we will see that Philology is a "project", in conformity with the objectives of the Critical Theory, with predetermined political intents, pre-designed plans for insinuation and establishment of contradictions. The question has been concerning the very professional ethics and responsibility of Philology itself. In such a situation, a "compromise" is generally made as suggested by (Gadamer, 1996). In his *Truth and Method*, Gadamer concludes as "Thus there is undoubtedly no understanding that is free from all prejudices, however much the will of our knowledge must be directed toward escaping their thrall. Throughout our investigation, it has emerged that the certainty achieved by using scientific methods does not suffice to guarantee truth. This especially applies to the human sciences, but it does not mean that they are less scientific; on the contrary, it justifies the claim to the special human significance that they have always made. The fact that in such knowledge the knowers own coming into play certainly shows the limits of the method, but not of science. Rather, what the tool of the method does not achieve—must—and really can—be achieved by a discipline of questioning and inquiring, a discipline that guarantees truth. (Gadamer, 1996)." Sheldon Pollock writes, (Pollock, 2015, b. 114), "Over the past two centuries, an impressive body of Western scholarship has been produced exploring the structure of this intricate and sophisticated system of language analysis. What is astonishing, however, even to specialists in the field, is "how little scholarship we possess— at least scholarship that is historically deep, systematically ordered, and conceptually rich— on the other traditional Indian forms of language- and- text analysis, beyond the phonology and morphology constituting the sphere of traditional grammar, that take us into domains we would include under any reasonable definition

of Philology— one that demands, not a specific set of methodological or theoretical features invariable across all time and space, but the broader concern with making sense of texts." Interestingly, however, while pleading for Philology before the American Universities recently, Pollock has confessed: " As for Philology, its contemporary form is generally un-theoretical, un-modern, un-trans, and un-cool, it has now been buried at the bottom of the... (Pollock. 2015)." The fact is that, given the present state of Philology, as in the Critical Theory, there is no single "correct" method of text-analysis, but many methods, with the possibility of complete inconsistency in drawing conclusions and interpretations.

Below we will consider a deconstruction exercise of a Philological project, just to know how philologists "make or create a sense" from the text and to have an idea which way to proceed to correct the errors.

4.1.0. Deconstructing a Philology Project

What follows is based on Reinhold Grünendahl's 'Post-Philological Gestures', (Grünendahl, 2010). Our aim is to "look by illustration" into what is behind the curtain in the Philological drama of making 'sense' of the texts. Since what is to come up in this section below may be disturbing to few, in order to eliminate even a single chance of alleged misrepresentation or misinterpretation, I have preferred direct quotes from the said article. It is synoptic here; the paper can be referred to for details.

On what Philology is he quotes Bernard Cerquiglini's *In Praise of the Variant*, (Cerquiglini, 1999, 49), which claimed to be a "Critical History of Philology". Cerquiglini defines Philology as:

4.1.1. "Philology is a bourgeois, paternalist, and hygienist system of thought about the family; it cherishes filiation, tracks down adulterers, and is afraid of contamination. It's thought is based on what is wrong (the variant being a form of deviant behavior), and it is the basis for a positive methodology."

The peer response to Cerquiglini's book may or may not have been positive but, as Grünendahl writes, "What has been considered most "Critical" about it is the "*degree of its selectiveness*", (Busby, (ed.).1993. 31), his stance can be assumed to have

gone down well with the numerous schools of contemporary "Critical Theory" that hark back to Foucault, be it directly, or indirectly, for instance, via Edward Said's *Orientalism*?" Out of Philological responsibilities of textual editing, textual criticism, amending, reading etc., (Grünendahl, 2010) begins with 'recent charges against Textual criticism in Indology and cites Peter van der Veer, (van der Veer, 2000), for intentional "hierarchization" in dealing with postcolonial assertion that,'

4.1.2. " (the) 'Philological project' of editing Hindu texts (...) is a construction of a Sanskrit canon that privileges a "classical age" before A.D. 1200 and marginalizes or ignores (...) literature written in modern Indian languages, such as Tamil, Bengali, or Urdu"

4.1.3 On." the term "Philological project": it presupposes an unwarranted degree of "political" intentionality and consensus among philologists, be it of the "paternalist", colonialist," or "nationalist" variety".

4.1.4. "... According to postcolonial theory, to entail "a violent hierarchy, in which one term of the opposition is always dominant". (Ashcroft, et al. 2000. p. 24, quoted in Grünendahl, 2010)

4.1.5. Probably the most important observation put forth by Grünendahl is, "It certainly does not provide for the possibility that Philology 'could have a purpose in itself' apart from supposedly serving master plans of another order." points (Grünendahl, 2010).

4.1.6. He points, "... it would be futile to exhaust oneself in the tedious correction of factual errors and distortions, because the postcolonial charge gathers its momentum outside the sphere of prosaic factuality, preferably by means of subtle insinuation".

The two examples given below from the same source show the "intentionality" and "insinuation" in the Philological projects.

4.1.7. *Example 1.*

'The postcolonial leitmotif "hierarchization" manifests itself in Peter van der Veer, (van der Veer, 2000) and, (Sugirtharajah, 2003). He applies their stance such that,

(i).' That "MaxMüller accorded a privileged position to the Sanskrit R̥gVeda while ignoring the "Tamil Veda";

(ii).' That he had privileged the written word and marginalized oral tradition;' and

(iii). that he had privileged the Veda, "thus delegitimizing other textual and oral forms of knowledge",

They try to show "a violent hierarchy", under the postcolonial Theory, "in which one term of the opposition is always dominant". (Ashcroft, 2000. 24, quoted in Grünendahl, 2010).

4.1.8. Further, van der Veer maintains that in "all Philological gestures, we may glimpse the nationalist gesture," and "insinuates a connection between the colonial, textualizing project of modernity and a supposed Romantic German search for self-definition."

4.1.9. *Example 2.*

To illustrate another "Philology project", we summarize another example from (Grünendahl, 2010). Peter van der Veer "creates an impression" that", the search for the "golden age of Indo-European civilization in Sanskrit 'Urtexts' ultimately fed into a larger discourse of nationalism, in which Indian philologists like Vishnu Sitaram Sukthankar, first editor in chief of the *Mahābhārata*, "used Philology in the way the Germans used it in their own country".

(...) Sanskrit Philology provided (Indian philologists) with the tools to dig up the origin and essence of the nation, that is, the Hindu nation."

And that, "they constructed a Hindu nationalist "imaginary", a selective archive of India's past"... and thus "the Critical edition of India's historical landscape, which reached a high pitch in the (...) destruction of Babar's Mosque in Ayodhya, is the site of struggle, the site of difference."

We can see how prejudiced and unscientific are the 'Philological projects', biased in textual Critical history and interpretation, where the creation of a Critical edition of the *Mahābhārata* is corroborated to be behind the demolition of the mosque structure on the disputed site of the *Rama janma bhumi*.

4.2.0. Observations made by Grünendahl on Critical Theory-Philology Project

4.2.1. Grünendahl observes, "To be sure, none of these post-Philological arguments are real to the point, but that is as close as the Critical theorist gets to the real thing. The basic misunderstanding that usually prevents an adequate assessment is the notion that textual criticism is about extracting a certain meaning from a text, while textual critics tend to follow the rule that questions concerning the meaning of a given text had better be postponed until its wording has been established as accurately as its textual tradition allows. Thus, van der Veer tries to discredit the Critical edition of the *Mahābhārata* not by pointing out editorial shortcomings, but by reading a "political" meaning into Sukthankar's "Philological project" that is unwarranted by anything Sukthankar himself has said, and then "contextualizing" it within Hindu nationalism - an equally unwarranted proposition." (Grünendahl, 2010).

This is how Philology, when taken as a 'Philological project' and not in the sense as expressed in (4.1.5), establishes conclusions by making "sense" from the textual history and its interpretation and that is why it is also called as, "a cultural technology of colonial rule". (Bernard, 1996, ix, Introduction by Dirks, quoted in Grünendahl, 2010). "Here van der Veer merely emulates Pollock's "Deep Orientalism", the most notorious example of this kind of discourse strategy.

4.2.2. Therefore, Grünendahl concludes as "This brings me to the epistemological level. On the one hand, the postcolonial charge associates the "Philological project" with *Realpolitik*. At the same time, by reducing its methodology to mere "gestures", affiliating it to "German Romanticism", and eventually making it part and parcel of "the Hindu nationalist imaginary", the factual basis of textual criticism is disputed. It's very reality is called into question by little more than the lavish use of inverted commas and words to that effect, such as "construct", *imaginaire*, etc. Consequently, the Critical theorist can hardly be expected to enter into a detailed discussion of the actual "Philological handiwork of Critical editions, etymology, historical grammar and the like, because that could be seen as attributing some substance to them after all — which is incompatible with the epistemological premise that reduces any notion of the factual nature of texts to a mere "religion of the text," as Cerquiglini puts it. (Grünendahl, 2010).

5.0.0 Sanskrit Knowledge System: *ādhyātmika* tradition²

After the methodological foundations, some concepts in Critical Theory and Philology, some of

² In Indian culture there is no way to escape -- even a नास्तिक cannot be stamped as अधार्मिक (' धर्म चरति ' ठक् , न धार्मिकः अधार्मिकः) । Because भागवतम् (6&7) puts him under वैरभक्ति - eligible for मोक्ष due to hostility with विष्णु । Panini rules - ' अस्ति नास्ति दिष्टं मतिः ' ठक् - Patanjali cracks a joke - कुंभकारे अपि प्राप्नोति ? - a कुंभकार has got the मति ' I am a कुंभकार ' ! Panini apparently does not say or suggest - what मति is अस्ति / नास्ति । Commentators say - it is परलोक । ' नास्तिको वेदनिन्दकः ' - मनुः । Let us take विज्ञानम् --- शिल्पम् and शास्त्रम् -- वीणावादनम् (' तदस्य शिल्पम् ' ठक् - वैणिकः) । अश्वशास्त्रम् , काकशास्त्रम् , गजशास्त्रम् लोहशास्त्रम् , धनुर्विद्या , स्थापत्यम् etc. But in every system/school there is धर्म associated . In आयुर्वेद also there is the discussion of पञ्चविंशतितत्त्वानि etc . व्याकरणम् has got two purposes - धर्म and अर्थबोधकत्वम् - but it will be अर्थजरतीयम् (only one part of the lady is liked and the rest is not). Indian culture stands on four pillars - धर्म - अर्थ - काम - मोक्ष । In स्वर्गारोहणपर्व of भारतम् , व्यास shouts -- ऊर्ध्वबाहुः विरौमि एष न हि कश्चित् शृणोति माम् । धर्मात् अर्थश्च कामश्च स धर्मः किं न सेव्यते ? ब्राह्म्याः - are those who care only for अर्थ and काम । We believe in कर्मसिद्धान्त । Unless and until 'the other person' comes with a viable alternative (till today he could not and I do not believe that he will come with one tomorrow) he also has to follow our theory. Then this life is bound with कर्म and as such there is nothing like profane. This is the uniqueness of Indian culture - this discussion should be an eyeopener to ' others ' . Let them first study all the 14 विद्यास्थानानि । (BVP, 2016)

their uses and abuses, it is now time to consider our *ādhyātmika*³ tradition. For, we will confine ourselves here only to the application of the Critical-Philology-Paradigm to the Sanskrit Knowledge System. We know that once defined according to the Critical Philology Paradigm, interpretations become self-propagating within the same Paradigm and its very assumptions become settled in our minds as presuppositions. This very fact has been behind all the numerous misinterpretations, which have occurred since Indological studies in the West. Once the basic assumptions are explicit and we have understood their applicability and errors involved, chances of further misinterpretations become lesser unless the interpreter has some "vested interest project" in his mind.

To begin me is picking a thread from a lecture delivered by Pollock, "The *Ends of Man at the End of Premodernity*". Twelfth Gonda Lecture, Dec.3rd, 2004, Royal Netherlands Academy of Arts and Sciences. Amsterdam. (Pollock, 2005). However, before that, let us see what Jan Gonda himself has said. He writes, " ... who take cognizance of the moot points and questions under discussion among Vedic and historians of Indian thought will have noticed that our knowledge of, and insight into Vedic religion largely depends on a correct understanding of a considerable number of Indian words and phrases, many of which have now been debated for nearly a century. They will have observed that rarely opinions on the exact sense of important religious terms continue to diverge widely, and in other cases, solutions offered with much self-confidence and suggestiveness appear to be, sooner or later, open to justifiable criticism."

³ "What characteristics *lakshaNa* our Vedic tradition assigns to some literature, for it to be classified as "*ādhyātmika*". Our Vedic tradition approaches this issue in many ways, such that its classification into Trivarga (*Dharma, Artha* and *Kama*) related and *Chaturtha varga* (*Moksha*) related. When applied to *rasavatkaavyas*, *kaavyas* whose *angirasa* is one of the five (*S'ringaara, KaruNa, Veera, Adbhuta and Haasya*) of the Eight (the other three being *Raudra, Bhayaanaka and Beebhatsa*) *rasas* fall in the *trivarga* domain. *Kaavyas* with *S'aanta* or *Bhakti* as the *angirasa* fall in the *chaturtha varga* category. Even in the *trivarga* category, the *kaarya* (action) is usually to attain *artha* and *kaama* within the bounds of or following the path of *dharmā* only. *Adhikaari* (target audience) is a *dharmabaddha* individual. That is why, *dharmaviruddha s'ringaara* is one of the kinds of *s'ringaara rasaabhaasa* (apparent but not real *s'ringaara rasa*). (BVP, 2016).

(Gonda, 1962, 243-73). On which Pollock, having his Critical-Philology methodology under his belt, says in his aforesaid Gonda Memorial lecture, "This kind of care for detail - this artisanal mastery - does tend to focus the mind ... did not take much to convince me that this mode of inquiry is an absolutely necessary condition of our disciplinary practice." (Pollock, 2005). "We can write this intellectual history because there is a history to Sanskrit intellection." He says further, "...we can write a history of Sanskrit learning in the 'late premodern,' or 'early modern,' period (c.1550-1750) - taking these terms for the moment in a strictly chronological and "value-neutral sense" as virtually synonymous with pre-colonial, and thereby suspending judgment about these centuries as ..." "We have seen, however, that "value neutrality" is not possible in the Critical theoretic methods under Philology, where the latter is a "project", as we now know, with a specific value bias and intent for insinuation.

Now, the reason behind Pollock's confinement to, while taking Foucauldian process as stated in the beginning, as analogy for Indian intellectual tradition, the aesthetics, form (of the text) and its historicity while dealing with Sanskrit texts under Critical Theory Paradigm can now well be understood through the way Marxism considers literature, see (2.10.0.). For, we consider here D.D. Kosambi, a mathematician by profession, a Marxist by persuasion, and a Sanskritist. Why choose Kosambi to show the Marxist interpretation of Sanskrit? It can be justified well as we know about his Critical editions of Bhartṛhari's 300 epigrams (*Śatakātṛaya*) and a twelfth-century anthology of classical Sanskrit epigrams (*Subhāṣitaratnakoṣa*) won him high approval from Sanskritists all over the world. He was a co-translator of Bhāsa's play, *Avimāṛaka*. He wrote two highly influential but controversial books on Indian history, (Kosambi 1975) and (Kosambi 1972). For further support see, (Pollock, 2008; Thapar, 2016; Goldman, s2016; Chakrabarty, 2016). Kosambi divided Sanskrit into prose *śāstra*, for facts and poetry *kāvya* for creativity (see Vico and Marx above), and gave weight to the latter. The same has been followed by Pollock, (Pollock, 2005) also based on the "science of imagination" for "creativity" in Vico, and the power to communicate, an attribute so significant in the Critical Theory. As a Marxist, Kosambi was very critical of the continuation of Sanskrit in India even after the rise of local vernaculars. In his overall view, Sanskrit was just a complimentary.

He writes, "At its best, Sanskrit literature is exquisite, with an "intricate pattern of beauty". Even at its best, it does not give the depth, simplicity of expression, the grandeur of spirit, the real greatness of humanity that one finds in the Pali *Dhammapada*, Dante is the *Divine Comedy* or Bunyan's *Pilgrim's Progress*. It is the literature of and for a class, not a people." (Kosambi, 1975, 283). What makes Kosambi's judgment of Sanskrit literature as a whole so significant is his distinct point of view, which can be encapsulated in a single question: does the work in question reflect, or at least show acquaintance with common people and women and their way of life? Kosambi viewed history too in the same light. "There is no need to dig into the *Gītā* or the Bible for an ethical system sandwiched with superstition. Such books can still be enjoyed for their aesthetic value" (Kosambi 1962, 37). He praises Patañjali's *Mahābhāṣya*, not only for its intrinsic merit but also for the fact that it "gains its strength and charm from a wealth of references to common life", (Kosambi, 1975, 282). *Śūdraka* is praised for the Prakrit with "provincial variations" that seems to be modeled upon life (Kosambi 1972, 202). Although the life of Harṣa is, generally speaking, useless to the historians, Kosambi (1972, 203) notes that "it contains priceless descriptions, as of the misery, panic, and havoc caused by the devastating march of a friendly army through its own territory". Kosambi is of the opinion that "Jayadeva had had an entirely different career from the other *Sena* court poets, who he joined in later life". He expected and appreciated the graphic portrayal of common life in literature and this is why he valued the *jātivraja* (Kosambi 1975, 280). Thus, we find, form, aesthetics, and dialectical historical materialism dominates here.

As a Marxist, being against Indian "transcendentalism, idealism and metaphysics", (Kosambi 1972, 207) has no sympathy for the "divine but rather scrambled message" of the *Gītā*, he declares, "The incongruities of the *Gītā* are entirely "in the Indian character"; but the Indian character was not fully set in its familiar mold till the feudal period. When gunpowder had blown Arjuna's bow and later feudalism off the map, the Indian intellectual still turned instinctively to the *Gītā* to find some way of coping with patriotic needs in the new world of ..." (Kosambi, 1972, 209). He says the merciless class analysis of the whole of Sanskrit literature need not affect the aesthetic appeal of particular works. Artistry too may very well be prized in its own terms without prejudice. This is why Kosambi could declare with

impunity: "We do not dismiss great writing because it is class literature" and that is why Kosambi could and did find many Sanskrit works both historically significant and aesthetically satisfying as Marx and Engels, and their adherents like Georg Lukács and Thomson, found in classical Greek literature. It is just a glimpse of a Marxist's view towards Sanskrit. This illustration of the Marxist interpretation of Sanskrit fills the gap between the Critical Theory and the Marxism with respect to Sanskrit in particular since the introduction to the concepts and foundations of Marxism and Critical Theory has been a general one and without any reference to Sanskrit.

In the same line of action Pollock organizes his exploration in Sanskrit around *puruṣārtha*, (Pollock, 2005), but before we proceed we must have in our mind that our tradition has always been for the "Cosmic Whole". Western Indologists fail miserably in 'accommodating' the Indian notion of 'transcendence' as defined by a vision of the cosmic whole, into their Critical theoretic Paradigm for various reasons we are already familiar by now. Their notion of 'transcendence' and "consciousness" are based on the grounds of cognition, as adopted in "Vico-Spinoza-Marx-Critical Theoretic-Philological Project-Paradigm". From Vico, from Marx, and from the Critical Theory we know that the Indian idea of "transcendence" has been assumed away. The transcendence and consciousness which the Critical Theory-Philology Project-Paradigm speak of under various "Neo" religious and political creations are determined by socio-cultural forces in the society and the words certainly misrepresent related Indian notions. From Marxist Dialectical-Historical Materialism and its assimilation into the foundation of Critical Theory and subsequent postmodern, poststructuralist developments as summarized, we understand that "historicity" lies at the heart of the whole Critical Paradigm including Philology.

Pollock organizes his exploration around *puruṣārtha*
puruṣārtha = kāma + artha + dharma

Pollock considers *puruṣārtha* as historically core concept and divides his analysis into *kāma*, *dharma* and *artha* as:

- (i) *kāma: alaṅkāra śāstra and the End of Literary Theory*
- (ii) *Dharma: mīmāṃsā and the End of Moral Theory*

(iii) *Artha: rāja dharma śāstra* and the End of Political Theory

(iv) He leaves moksha the supreme end aimed to attain through above three ends.

Let us examine why has been *mokṣa* excluded? To answer, let us begin with the concept of *kāla*, (Prasad,1992), (misleadingly translated as phenomenal time) and then corroborated to the much sought after "historicity" and the *dharma*, (again misleadingly translated as religion). It must be understood that *dharma* cannot be translated as it is pregnant with meaning and conforms to meaning - *dhriyate anena iti dharmah*. If *dharma* is translated as a religion it will be wrong as its back translation fails such that, religion = *matam* (not *dharma*), *matam* means *iṣṭam*, i.e., liked by 'some' people, not all. Local, not universal, and historically linear, whereas, *dharma* is universal. All we have is *sanātana dharmah*, *sanātanaḥ*, (which is undefinable under Critical theoretic Paradigm)= *nityaḥ dharma = dharma*, and the same is *anādi* in *sanātana dharma*, even if considered manifested as external, we have to accept certain things as *anādi*, (this contradicts to linear historicity of Critical Theory- Philology Project- Paradigm the as we have seen above). It is with *Advait Vedānta*, where we accept six *anādi*, the *karma* of *anādi jīva*, is *anādi* too. Such a *dharma*, that is *anādi* (beginning-less) is supported by *Veda jAtyekavachanam* that is *also anādi*. In order to arrest the cycle of death and birth, one has to realize the *brahmn* the same is called *mokṣa*. Critical Theory Paradigm fails in conceptualizing such situation and therefore, assumes it non-existent. Practitioners of Critical Theory- Philology Project- Paradigm have no way to deal with it and that is why Pollock says that 'these concepts have, historically been under reconstruction but never discussed', (Pollock, 2005). "The "silence" is arguably due to the fact that by then the *puruṣārtha* had taken on the character of common sense. The "truth" is that for reasons and limitations due to foundational presumption and axioms in the Critical - Philological Paradigm, its practitioners fail to accommodate moksha, being transcendental, despite being the end aim in the Indian tradition to be attained through above three ends, *kāma*, *dharma*, and *artha*. Since Pollock has adopted the Critical theoretic Paradigm, to escape from this Paradigm is to escape from any of its analytics chosen to apply. Thus, he confines himself to 'pleasure, power and moral order' and finds it somehow, deeply interconnected and immersed in

the concept of *puruṣārtha* in order to fit it into his Critical Paradigm. However, he points out in footnote 8 that the history of the expansion of three ends to include fourth, *mokṣa* has been understudied. Amarsimha, (*NAmalingAnuSasana* 2.7.58), of the 5th century, knew it but its origin still unclear and Pollock tries to find its origin in *mīmāṃsā*.

Again, handicapped by the assumptions of the Critical Theory Philology Paradigm, its practitioners seems to be completely ignorant of the concept of time not only by Indian tradition, (Prasad, 1992) but even of his own Western tradition. On one hand, his Critical Paradigm rejects idealism and traditional Theory based on it, on the other hands depending on the same tradition Pollock finds *mīmāṃsā* problematic and sees fault in *mīmāṃsā* with respect to the historicity, in it. We know that *mīmāṃsā* is founded on two grounds:

- a) Dharma is a transcendent entity, and unknowable by any form of knowledge, not itself transcendent. This, according to Pollock, is postulated without substantiation, where, as a rule, transcendence is assumed away in Pollock's Critical methods, so he can never develop any explanation from within his adopted Paradigm.
- b) All cognitions must be accepted as true unless and until they are falsified by other cognitions.

For, as the Vedas are taken as *pramāṇa* of *dharma*, the *mīmāṃsaka* must establish the Vedas as transcendent. The Vedas refer to *pāramārthika* and *vyāvahārika* both and transcendence is established by postulating the Vedas as *akālika*, timeless and *apurushaya*, authorless but revealed. Note "Revealed" in the sense we use in Indian tradition, like *pāramārthika*, this too is not in the dictionary of Critical Theory- Philology Project- Paradigm and therefore, practitioners find the arguments offered by the *mīmāṃsaka* to establish the above wholly unconvincing. On it, Pollock writes, "It is argued that the Vedas are transcendent by reason of their anonymity. Had they been composed by men, albeit long ago, there is no reason why the memory of these composers should not have been preserved to us." He concluded, "The world of late premodern Indian knowledge is vast, and finding some way to narrow it down is essential. I do that here by choosing 'what seems to me' to be representative persons and environments. Regional formations of epoch show divers modes of political

organization and hence of patronage structures."
(Pollock 2005.12).

6.0.0. Evaluation

A summary of the basic methodological sequence is given in the table below.

It becomes clear that this Critical Theory-Philology-Paradigm is a Paradigm the world view of which is limited by its own assumptions. It assumes the intractable part of knowledge as non-existent. A question arises, as to, why that idealistic-metaphysical part was excluded. The answer lies in the "intent" of the analyst, determined by the intent of the Paradigm, the dialectical materialism; and Marxism of various shades. Depending upon at which stage the Paradigm is in operation, it plays a big role in dialectical materialism in analyzing the power-culture structure of the society. The implication becomes extra harsh when it involves the Leftist prejudices combined with the Critical Theory-Philology-Paradigm. It began with Marx and despite all the later developments and post-structuralist developments; the Leftist character has remained intact.

One can pick any work done through the Critical Theory-Philology-Paradigm analytics, and if he or she has an understanding in the line examined in this paper, one can easily identify the elements of contradiction, political intents, the Form-aesthetics-historicity based analytic structure in the Philological activity with the text concerned. Just take the example of a book edited by Sheldon Pollock. The title of the book, "*Epic and Argument in the Sanskrit Literary History*", in no way, gives any hint that the analytics and interpretation in the book have been Marxian. Now just turn the leaves, the first list of references which comes in the very beginning of the book, gives 'Kosambi and the Marxist Critique of Sanskrit Literature', and at the end, the book includes a paper on the Hymns of Rig Veda by Romila Thapar, a Marxist historian in India. Any reader unaware of the intents and ideological affiliation of the authors is bound to take it as a correct interpretation based on the original Indian tradition, but, in fact, it is not. We can understand now what type of interpretation can one expect if the methodology itself is Marxist, and the interpreters have Marxist political affiliation and have not followed the professional ethics of at least informing the reader of the ideology involved in interpretations. Most often, we find another layer of deception in such studies. No original text is generally supplied along with the interpretation, which means, the reader has to trust what the interpreter has said. It is well known that even pure etymological meanings of such texts are contested, lest aside the discretionary Philological "making

sense" with politically fully charged with the Marxist power-culture intent. This shows clearly that whenever the analysis and textual criticism of Indian Scriptures are performed under the Critical Theory-Philology Paradigm, no matter a Western does it or Eastern scholar if he or she is trained in the said Paradigm; the conclusion is inevitably contrary to our traditional interpretations. This is because the transcendental ideology, inherent in our sacred scriptures in Sanskrit are assumed away at the outset by presumption under the Critical Theory-Philology-Project-Paradigm and what remains to analyze is the Sanskrit literature as a record of social dialectics.

We observe further with the examples of Philological project and the Marxist treatment of Sanskrit as evident from the representative works in Sanskrit by Kosambi; cited above, that rather than a scientific curiosity, there is evident a clear political intent, deliberate insinuation, prejudiced fixation of causality and many other discretionary acts enabled by the "non-unique" nature of the Critical theories. Moreover, a lack of any standard methodology or technique to judge if the Philological activities and the conclusion were drawn are correct, make it easy to induct vested interests and hence come to the desired conclusions. This is why Pollock says all interpretations of a text are correct. The question is can a student in his department pass an examination by writing whatever interpretation of the text asked to interpret in the question paper. It is academically absurd proposition showing an examiner's state of mental "undecidability".

We cannot ignore the observation made by Grünendahl who points out, "Apart from being accused of "secret complicities" with colonial power, knowledge is simultaneously reduced to mere interpretation and, according to the deconstructionist axiom, and all interpretation is a misinterpretation. Thus, all knowledge is provisional or hypothetical, with the obvious exception of the deconstructionist's knowledge of this being so; all readings are misreadings since no reading can escape correction and consequently, all texts are subject to deconstruction, Critical editions being just one subset." (Grünendahl, 2010).

Objectively speaking, we can approach this limitation as a methodological handicap because, even if we assume for a moment that all though process including consciousness is determined by

the psycho-biological process in nature, the idealistic part which this Paradigm ignores, by assuming non-existent must have emerged from the same materialistic psycho-biological process. This leaves us, however, with the possibility of modifying the fundamental axioms and assumptions to enable assimilation of the excluded facet into the Paradigm. Since we as Indians, are the ones most adversely affected by the misinterpretations or insinuation of our sacred texts, of the ideologies they embody and the Indian tradition as a whole we own, the bulk of the responsibility in this respect falls upon us.

For this, a careful study and analysis of the analytics in the Critical Theory- Philology Project-Paradigm keeping of specific texts in mind is needed. All the dimensions of textual criticism and Philological practices need to be faithfully considered so that near correct interpretation of the texts can be reached. Therefore, it is not like the discretionary "making sense", as Pollock seeks to prove his conclusions.

With a view to upgrade and develop our own Indian version of holistic Philology, (not in the sense of the Liberation Philology, (Pollock, 2012), where Pollock seems to adopt the Liberation Theology of the Marxist-Church combine, (Löwy, 2006), as an analogy. It may be along the line suggested by Prof. Aklujkar, though discretely, but which can be put together in seamless alignment. He had suggested three main dimensions of direct relevance to the development of Indigenous Philology, grammar, sociolinguistics and the history of ancient Sanskrit literature. (Aklujkar, 1996, 2003, 2004).

It is necessary to proceed as to,

(i) extend the basic presumptions of the Critical theory so that "transcendental and ideological" which has been assumed away can be assimilated into the analytic paradigm of the critical theory. It is because we accept the Critical theory as one of the effective methods to analyze the social phenomena without any prejudice against Marxism but simultaneously, we cannot be blind under Marxism to ignore or assume the other side of reality as non-existent. In fact, there is a paradox, which practitioners of the Critical Theory-Philology Project-Paradigm do not generally mind, and it is the fact that they use the same logical tools and methods they did reject under criticism of ideology and rationality, to justify their

arguments with whatever nomenclature they wish to use.

(ii) For the above-proposed extension, we may need a reconsideration to revise and for upgrade the grammar and semantics and sociolinguistics for our traditional texts. For example, the question raised by Prof. Aklujkar, 'Can the Grammarian's Dharma be a Dharma for all?' (Aklujkar, 2004), may prove to be a core one in the process.

(iii) Historicity in Indian Tradition has been variously questioned by the Western practitioners of CPP. Pollock had some reservations on Prof. Aklujkar's suggestion on it, (Pollock, 2005).

We know, Indian knowledge system has its own conception of time, (Prasad,1992), and historicity, failing the applications of scientific methods which Frankfurt School classified as the "Traditional method" applied to phenomenal investigations. Historicity is taken in Pollock is like "local analysis" in contrast to "global analysis", in the mathematical sense and with his attempt as a literal generalization of conclusions of the part to the whole. Arvind Sharma, (Sharma, .2003), has examined the issue of historicity. This needs a careful further study.

(iv) The Critical theory is non-unique; every new situation requires a new Critical theory, new, modified or a combination of various existing. The absence of a "standard" this is the biggest drawback of the Critical Theory. This gives enormous vacuum for further exploration to find a holistic alternative.

For the damage already done to our texts and tradition, I agree with Grünendahl when he says, "... it would be futile to exhaust oneself in the tedious correction of factual errors and distortions, because the postcolonial charge gathers its momentum outside the sphere of prosaic factuality, preferably by means of subtle insinuation, (Grünendahl, 2010). It is, therefore, better to make a necessary overhaul of our tools and techniques of textual criticism and interpretations and upgrade and develop our own Philology for our own texts.

Lastly, I end this paper with a fine prescription from Prof. V.S.Agarwala, "There is only one solution", points he, "to this difficulty. We should now begin to study more closely the explanations of the mystical Vedic terminology offered in the indigenous literature, especially the *Brāhmana* and

the *āranyakas*, which are replete with interpretational material that has remained useless in the absence of the *ādhyātmika* school of Vedic interpreters. Unfortunately, there are many today who could claim to represent the *Aitihāsikas* and *ākhyānvidas* of Yaska, but very few who could say that they are carrying on the torch of the *ādhyātma-vidas* referred to in the *Nirukta*." (Agarwala, 1939).

As for now, unless and until a Philology is developed and made capable enough to assimilate the idealism and transcendence in its true sense, its practitioners must show a little academic honesty, at least, to confess that whatever they have been writing or writing, are the Marxist interpretation of the subject matter.

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